

in the check, NCU, SCU, and LCU compared to MBU, PUS, and USG (see table).

With drainage, dry matter yield and N uptake with SCU equaled that with PUS and MBU. LCU and NCU also showed a similar trend. Dry matter yield and N uptake were significantly depressed

with USG, and equaled the dry matter yield and N uptake of the check. Dry matter yield and N uptake of the check were twice what they were with no drainage.

With drainage, the low dry matter yield and N uptake with USG was caused

by cumulative leaching losses of total N (urea + NH_4^+ -N) (see figure). Nitrogen leaching losses were 62.1% for USG, 19.1% for NCU, 16.9% for LCU, 14.3% for PUS, and 13.0% for MBU. No leaching losses of urea or NH_4^+ -N were recorded for SCU.

Effect of micronutrients and farmyard manure on yield and micronutrient content of rice

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A field experiment to determine the effect of micronutrients and farmyard manure (FYM) was conducted on a sodic soil with sand + silt 85.4%, clay 14.6%, CaCO_3 2.45%, pH 10.6, exchangeable sodium percentage 92, CEC 10.0 meq/100 g, gypsum requirement 25 t/ha; and DTPA extractable Fe, Mn, and Zn 3.5, 4.2, and 0.45 ppm, respectively, at Gudha experimental farm of CSSRI.

The experiment was in a split-plot design with 4 replications of 5 micronutrient treatments: T1, control, no micronutrient; T2, 20 ppm Fe; T3, 20 ppm Mn; T4, 5 ppm Zn; and T5, 20 ppm Fe + 20 ppm Mn + 5 ppm Zn and 0 and 10 t FYM/ha. FYM contained 0.85% N, 0.35% P, 0.78% K, 0.35% Ca, 0.24% Mg, 0.22% S, 52 ppm Zn, 125 ppm Mn, 10 ppm Cu, and 320 ppm Fe. Fifty percent of the gypsum requirement was broadcast and mixed and all plots received 150 kg N/ha as urea. Micronutrient sources were $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Plot size was 40m². Micronutrients, FYM, and 75 kg N/ha were broadcast and disced into the soil. Plots

Effect of micronutrients and FYM on rice yield and micronutrient concentration.

Treatment	FYM rate (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha)		Micronutrient concn (ppm)						
		Grain	Straw	Zn			Fe		Mn	
				Leaves	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
Control	0	5.0	8.0	8.5	8.1	10.5	45	335	40	285
	10	5.3	8.3	9.6	9.9	12.8	55	375	48	340
Fe (20 ppm)	0	5.0	8.0	8.4	8.0	10.4	52	360	46	295
	10	5.4	8.4	9.8	10.0	13.1	68	415	52	365
Mn (20 ppm)	0	5.2	8.2	8.6	8.5	10.6	46	340	51	315
	10	5.6	8.7	11.2	11.8	18.2	55	380	58	425
Zn (5 ppm)	0	5.6	8.7	15.5	12.9	25.4	45	340	42	280
	10	6.0	9.1	20.6	15.8	30.5	56	380	48	345
Fe+Mn+Zn	0	6.0	9.1	15.4	12.8	26.8	50	365	55	325
	10	6.0	9.3	21.8	15.1	31.8	68	425	62	480
CD (0.05) for comparing										
FYM level means		0.22	0.35	1.2	0.9	0.7	8	20	6	18
Micronutrient means		0.33	0.44	1.0	0.8	1.6	5	14	3	10

were irrigated and 30-day-old Jaya rice seedlings were transplanted 15 Jul 1979. The remaining 75 kg N was topdressed in 2 equal splits at 3 and 6 weeks of crop growth. Leaf samples of 30-day-old plants (3d and 4th leaves from the top) were collected and plant samples were taken at harvest 1 Nov 1979.

Zn application significantly enhanced the grain and straw yield (see table). Fe and Mn did not affect yield but the highest yield was recorded when these elements were applied with Zn.

Crop growth was poor in plots without Zn and symptoms of moderate

Zn deficiency were noticed at early growth stage (25-30 days). FYM significantly enhanced the yield, irrespective of the micronutrient treatment, possibly because of the increased availability of Zn caused by its application. Zn concentration in 30-day-old leaves was less than the critical 10 ppm value in plots where it was not applied because available soil Zn was less than the critical 0.55 ppm level. Application of Fe, Mn, and Zn enhanced their respective concentration in the crop. FYM also effectively increased micronutrient concentration in the crop.

Comparison of photoperiod-sensitive ratooned rice and normal sown aman rice

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Ratooned and normal sown aman rice varieties were compared. Photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties SR26B, FR13A, Tillakkachari and Achra 108/1 were sown on 14 Nov 1981 and harvested May 1982. Ratooned tillers grew in the fields. A sim-

Comparison of photoperiod-sensitive ratooned and normal sown aman rice, Chinsurah, India, 1981-82.

Variety	Aman sown rice				Ratooned rice			
	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Yield (t/ha)
SR26B	146	22	7	3.7	158	24	11	2.5
FR13A	113	22	8	3.8	146	25	11	3.0
Tillakkachari	142	24	9	3.8	170	26	13	5.0
Achra 108/1	132	25	7	3.9	170	27	11	4.8
Mean	133	23	8	3.7	161	26	12	3.8

ilar set of varieties was sown 17 Jul 1982 and their performance was compared to that of the ratooned crop.

Plant height, panicle length, and tiller number were higher for ratoons than for

normal sown man rice. Ratooned Tillakachari and Achra 108/1 yielded more than the aman sowing of the same varieties (see table). The mean yield of ratooned rice varieties equaled that of

normal sown rice, indicating the suitability of ratoon cultivation in lowland areas where flood or sudden water stagnation hampers the freshly planted rice crop during the wet season. □

Fungi-caused rotten disease of azolla

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In 1981, the fungus *Myrothecium* sp. was discovered to cause rotten disease of azolla. In 1982 azolla propagation in north-east Thailand was increased and an outbreak of rotten disease occurred. Damage was more severe than in 1981 and symptoms were different from those caused by *Myrothecium* sp. Disease samples were collected from a farmer's propagation pond in Sakolnakorn Province in Nov-Dec 1982. Six genera of fungi were isolated: *Myrothecium* sp., *Rhizoctonia* sp., *Sclerotium* sp., *Fusarium* sp., and two unidentified fungi. One unidentified genus had a yellow colony of mycelium, the other a black colony. All were grown on potato dextrose agar.

Healthy azolla was individually inoculated with the six isolated fungi and grown in a 38-cm-diameter pot. Each

Comparison of disease symptom development on *Azolla pinnata* after inoculation by selected fungi.

Fungus	Symptom development, (days after inoculation)			Azolla death (days after inoculation)	Azolla rotting (days after inoculation)	Disease appearance
	Leaf	Stem	Root			
<i>Rhizoctonia</i> sp.	2	2	2	3-4	5-7	Infected fern turned pale-brown in color, then brown to dark brown.
<i>Myrothecium</i> sp.	2	2	3	3-5	10-15	Infected fern turned grey-green in color, then grey-brown to dark brown.
<i>Sclerotium</i> sp.	7	-	-	-	-	Infected fern showed only small brown lesion on leaf.
<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	-	-	-	-	-	No symptom
Unidentified (yellow colony)	-	-	-	-	-	No symptom
Unidentified (black colony)	-	-	-	-	-	No symptom
Distilled water (control)	-	-	-	-	-	No symptom

treatment and a distilled water sprayed control was replicated four times. Disease development was recorded.

Rhizoctonia sp. damaged azolla most, causing infected ferns to rot 5-7 days after inoculation. *Myrothecium* sp.

caused rotting 10-15 days after inoculation (see table). *Sclerotium* sp. caused small brown lesions on the leaves 7 days after inoculation, but did not cause rotting. *Fusarium* sp. and the two unidentified fungi did not cause the disease. □

Effects of plant population and urea supergranule deep placement on rice yield

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We studied the effect of plant population and deep placement of urea supergranules (USG) on rice yield at Coimbatore in 1980 wet season and 1981 dry season (Jan-May). The soil was clay loam with pH 7.8, 0.38% carbon, and CEC 26.8 meq/100 g.

The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with four planting treatments in five replications. Plot size was .0 × 4.0 m. Heavy tillering rice Co 43 from the cross Dhasal/IR20 was planted

Effect of plant spacing and USG placement on rice panicles and grain yield of Co 43.^a

Spacing (cm)	Hills (no./m ²)	USG (no./4 hills)	Panicles/m ²		Panicle wt (g)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
			WS	DS	WS	DS	WS	DS
15 × 10	66	1	489	476	1.90	1.85	4.9	6.1
15 × 20	33	2	315	586	2.68	2.44	5.2	6.6
22.5 × 20	22	3	233	495	2.85	2.22	5.2	6.3
30 × 20	16	4	225	470	2.39	2.24	5.1	6.2
CD (0.05)	-	-	39	30	0.27	0.48	0.2	0.2

^aUrea supergranule (USG) at 75 kg N/ha was deep placed. WS = wet season, DS = dry season.

at 2 seedlings/hill. The table gives treatment details and number of panicles, panicle weight, and grain yield.

Results indicated that 20 × 15 cm spacing (33 plants/m²), or half the population of conventional spacing, gave significantly higher grain yield in both

seasons. Yield with 22 plants/m² equaled that of 33 plants/m² during wet season. However, yield with 33 plants/m² was significantly higher than with 22 plants/m² during dry season (see table).

The number of panicles/m² was significantly higher in a conventional plant-